

Micro- and macro-pragmatics: The interface between rhetoric, pragmatics, and critical discourse analysis

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Presuming two major interrelated and at the same time distinct perspectives on pragmatics, the current paper seeks to delineate the similarities and differences of dialectic versus dialogic pragmatics. It begins with a brief and informative overview of rhetoric and claims that rhetoric is essentially a kind of pragmatics where a rhetor carries dialectic into oration to challenge, sway, persuade, or defeat an adversary through elocution. It then moves on to a brief overview of dialogic pragmatics and argues that it builds on a cooperative dyad where the interlocutors work in tandem to co-create a dialogue. Assuming an inclusional distribution between the two, the paper concludes that dialectic pragmatics is essentially concerned with one form of intentionality and can therefore be called micro-pragmatics whereas dialogic pragmatics encompasses all forms of intentionality including that of rhetoric, and that it can therefore be called macro-pragmatics.

Keywords: Adversary; Dialectic Pragmatics; Dialogic Pragmatics; Rhetoric; Rhetorics

1. Introduction

Pragmatics—roughly defined as ‘the systematic study of intentions’ or ‘the systematic study, à la Levinson (1983), of ‘how speakers/hearers pair utterances/intentions with their appropriate contexts of use’—has a long history. It has essentially been a fundamental subject matter in philosophy *per se* since ancient Mesopotamia, Egypt, Greece, and Rome, but linguists have more recently shown a lot of interest in pragmatics as a subject matter in linguistics and the philosophy of language; it would, therefore, not be wrong if we claimed that, today, two major interrelated and at the same time distinct perspectives on pragmatics exist: (a) the philosophical perspective, and (b) the linguistic perspective (Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015b). This is by no means to deny the fact that other branches of science are also informed by pragmatics; politics, for instance and for the main part, revolves around the concepts of ‘pragmatism’ and ‘realism’, a discussion of which is beyond the scope of this paper.

In this paper, I will first present a brief overview of what I would like to call micro or dialectic pragmatics (i.e., Greek rhetoric). Then, I will move on to a discussion of macro or dialogic pragmatics and argue why I see Greek rhetoric as a subordinate to linguistic pragmatics. I will also present a brief overview of the major camps that exist within modern pragmatics and focus on two of the most recent ones: Mey's (2001) Pragmatic Act Theory, and Kecskes' (2013) Socio-Cognitive Approach.

2. Micro/Dialectic pragmatics: Oratory in Ancient Greece

'Pragmatics' comes from the Greek word "πραγματικός" (i.e., fit for action) and has to do with intentions/intentionality. It is deeply rooted in Greek rhetoric (or the art of persuading through eloquent speech) which, in turn, has its roots in Enheduanna's writings (Binkley, 2004a, 2004b; Hallo, 2004; Hoskisson & Boswell, 2004; Stark, 2008). Enheduanna, whose Akkadian writings formed the basics of Greek rhetoric, lived in ancient Mesopotamia. In this connection, it should be emphasized that Mesopotamian rhetoric comprised the five canons of (a) exordium, (b) argument, (c) peroration, (d) repetition, and (e) metonymy; a discussion of these canons is beyond the scope of this paper, but the interested reader may want to see Hallo (2004). The Neo-Assyrian Empire and ancient Egypt had also developed their own conceptions of rhetoric. Specifically, ancient Egypt considered five canons of rhetoric—i.e., (a) wise silence, (b) timing, (c) restraint, (d) fluency, and (e) truthfulness (cf. Hoskisson & Boswell, 2004). Moreover, it argued that eloquent speech should be used to support society, a position that was also held by the Chinese philosopher, Confucius (Stark, 2008).

Nevertheless, the earliest systematic study of rhetoric should be credited to the ancient Greeks. Even before Aristotle wrote his treaties on rhetoric, traces of rhetoric (or practical persuasion through eloquent speech) were visible in Homer's *Iliad* and *Odyssey*, which include examples that illustrate how eloquent speech has been used by such heroes as Achilles, Hector, and Odysseus. *Logôn techne* (meaning *skill with arguments* or *verbal artistry*) was the prototype for 'rhetoric' and was used in ancient Greece (a) to support political or judicial decisions in the then-emerging democratic polis, and (b) to develop and promulgate philosophical ideas (Binkley, 2004); the person who was skilled in using *Logôn techne*—later called rhetoric—was often called a 'rhetor' (Hallo, 2004; Hoskisson & Boswell, 2004; Stark, 2008). The job of the rhetor was to clarify arguments and give order to them; this stands in sharp contrast to today's often 'pejorative' connotation of the term rhetoric which implies a conscious attempt at obscuring the truth (Hoskisson & Boswell, 2004).

Anyway, many ancient Greeks engaged in rhetoric (e.g., Sophists, Isocrates, and Plato, among others), but the first scholar to approach the study of rhetoric in a systematic way was Aristotle, who argued that the 'practical intention' of rhetoric is to 'persuade' the audience (Binkley, 2004; Hallo, 2004; Hoskisson & Boswell, 2004; Stark, 2008). For Aristotle (1984), rhetoric and dialectic were arts of discourse production that worked in tandem. Rhetoric, à la Aristotle, had to do with practical matters. However, dialectic was mainly concerned with theoretical issues (Bizzell & Herzberg, 1990).

It would not, therefore, be wrong to claim that early interest in the notions of 'intentionality' and 'practicality', which lie at the heart of rhetoric, dates back to the time of Greek rhetoricians—and specifically Aristotle, and as we will see, Quintilian—whose job was to present their arguments in such an effective and irresistible way as to make their audience (a) accept the arguments, (b) adopt them, (c) act upon them, and (d) propagate and promulgate them (Allan, 2004; Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015). Needless to say, Greek rhetoric did indeed see the speaker as a 'fighter' whose fundamental job was to wield a persuasive language/oratory lasciviously loaded with undue exaggeration, pretension, bombast and display with the aim of influencing the thoughts and actions of the mob or an opponent. At the heart of this perspective on speech lies an 'adversary' whom the speaker is determined to challenge and defeat. As we will see below, Cooperation—one of the pedestals upon which Gricean pragmatics (cf. Grice, 1957, 1975) of the twentieth century stands—had no place in ancient Greek rhetoric. The Greek rhetorician saw himself—I am not able to use herself here since I could not find a female rhetorician in the extant literature on ancient Greek rhetoric—as a warrior who had just one mission to accomplish: to counter his opponent's point of view; Aristotle's 'speaker' would, nevertheless, unflinchingly carry dialectic into rhetoric (Allan, 2004; Barnes, 1984).

As such, Greek rhetoric was essentially the civic art—or craft—of persuasion aimed at civic engagement and action. Greek rhetoricians, and mainly the sophists, would undoubtedly use rhetoric to 'sway' the audience (Borchers, 2006; MacDonald, 2017; Walker, 2000) whereby getting them engaged in some course of action which quite often had a political aspiration and/or ambition. *Rhetoric*, written by Aristotle during the 4th century B.C., is perhaps the seminal work that depicts the basic tenets of this civic art. It presumes that language and persuasion are closely tied together.

To put it in a nutshell, Greek rhetoric is essentially based on two triangles: (a) the rhetorical triangle, and (b) the persuasion triangle. The former has three angles: (a) the orator/rhetor, (b) the audience, and (c) the topic. Likewise, the latter comprises three angles: (a) ethos, (b) logos, and (c) pathos. The orator brings the triangle of persuasion to bear on his/her delivery of the topic in such

a way as to sway the audience through language so that the audience would yield obedience and act the way the orator aspires after (MacDonald, 2017).

Ethos has to do with the orator's authoritativeness; trust should be built before the audience can be swayed or persuaded. The orator needs to establish credibility with the audience if he or she wants the audience to accept what he or she preaches. This, according to Aristotle, requires that the orator at least display (a) good will, altruism and philanthropy, (b) piety and virtue, and (c) practical intelligence. Once the audience sees the orator as a pious and intelligent authority, trust is built. On the other hand, pathos has to do with orator's ability and skill to build upon the audience's emotions and to elicit empathy/sympathy (Borchers, 2006). This often involves the use of rhetorical devices (e.g., metaphors, monotony, alliteration, anaphoric repetition, etc.) and poetic language. For instance, the notions of 'iconicity' and 'conceptual distance', à la Haiman (1983, 1992), have been used in King Jr.'s repetition of the phrase "One hundred years later" in his famous speech to appeal to the audience's emotions; listening to this repetitive phrase over and over again makes the audience feel a lack of progress in King Jr.'s oration which aspires after displaying a lack of progress in black civil rights through appealing to the audience's emotions by means of language. Finally, logos draws on inductive or deductive logic as well as other forms of reasoning to persuade the audience. Statistics, facts, examples, details, etc. that are used in academic writing fall in this category (cf. Birjandi et al., 2004).

Although Aristotle's *Rhetoric* was the seminal work that delineated the ABCs of Greek rhetoric (cf. Barnes, 1984), Quintilian is perhaps the most influential Roman scholar who revolutionized its tenets and moved it to another level. Before Quintilian, rhetoric was a civic art possessed by orators—mainly philosophers and logicians. However, Quintilian transformed it to a set of training methods that aimed at describing the processes of learning rhetorical discourse which could be used in educating new orators (Borchers, 2006; MacDonald, 2017; Walker, 2000). His five canons of rhetoric (i.e., invention, arrangement, style, memory, and delivery) were meant for purposes of education.

In simple terms, Quintilian's five canons hold that an argument needs to be 'invented' and 'organized' before it can finally be 'delivered'. Invention requires that the orator draw on a systematic search process, a range of reliable search methods, an effective way of discovering arguments, and so forth to invent the speech—remember that 'speech' was the default form of linguistic production in ancient Greece (Borchers, 2006). Once speech/oration is invented, its parts need to be rhetorically and coherently organized into a specific 'arrangement' that is simultaneously optimal, adequate and vital for the success of persuasion—a consideration that also lies at the heart of modern composition

and academic writing (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023). In this canon, the orator orders whatever arguments and thoughts he or she has discovered in the first canon in a specific, effective, adequate and optimal rhetorical organization. Arrangement often starts with an introduction (i.e., an appeal to ethics) and then proceeds with the main argument (i.e., the statement of facts, division, proof, and refutation) before it comes to a conclusion (or an appeal to the audience's emotions). As such, arrangement holds that an argument should begin with *ethos*, proceed with *logos*, and end in *pathos* (MacDonald, 2017). The third canon is style. This canon determines how the argument is delivered. Although style has to do with 'aesthetics' in modern times, in ancient Greece it was not ornamental; rather, it was part and parcel of eloquent argumentation (or 'elocution', if you will) which guaranteed the success of the orator's intention (i.e., persuasion); 'style' was a tradition that lived on to enter the Renaissance (MacDonald, 2017). Memory, the fourth canon, empowers the orator to store whatever information and arguments he or she has discovered in the first canon; in this connection, the orator (or the rhetor) can use 'mnemonic devices' which will make the memorization and retention of information and arguments easy. Without the aid of good memory, the orator is prone to error during his/her oration since good oration requires quick and clear thought (Walker, 2000). Finally, the fifth canon (i.e., delivery) determines how the argument/oration is enacted. Intense vocal training, body language, gestures, etc. are part and parcel of this canon, and a good orator is one who knows how to wield these 'metalinguistic weapons' to appeal to the emotions of the audience. It should be remembered that delivery is tied to *pathos*. To recapitulate, 'invention' and 'arrangement' have to do with actual fabrication of an argument whereas 'style', 'memory' and 'delivery' concern recitation (Walker, 2000). This means that ancient Greek rhetoric was, in essence, a process of 'fabrication' and 'recitation' which involved *ethos*, *logos* and *pathos*. In other words, the five canons of rhetoric go hand in hand to guide the crafting of an argument and function as a template that can be brought to bear on the teaching of rhetoric; nevertheless, they can also be utilized in discussions or evaluations of discourse (Borchers, 2006; MacDonald, 2017; Walker, 2000)—especially that of the opponent/adversary.

Rhetoric survived the passage of time to enter the twentieth century. It continued to be the central analytical method for the evaluation of the verbal arts but became quite scholastic. Nevertheless, its main concept—that of intentionality—has a direct bearing on what has come to be known as (linguistic) pragmatics; its scope was much narrower than that of (linguistic) pragmatics, though (see section 3 below).

The 'logos' part of Greek rhetoric has impacted our understanding of modern logic and truth conditions—and, whereby, our conceptions of some of the basic tenets of linguistic pragmatics and theories of semantics (cf. Ayer, 1936; Bacon,

1620; Chalmers, 2004, 2006; Davidson, 1967; Foster, 1976; Frege, 1879, 1906; Salmani Nodoushan, 2015b, 2018, 2022). Aristotle, of course, was mainly concerned about logical fallacies; his *Organon* is perhaps the first treatise on the issue of fallacies in logical argumentation. Nevertheless, Greek rhetoric has profoundly informed such areas of inquiry as critical discourse analysis (Battista, 2022; D'Avanzo, 2022; Fairclough, 1989; Raffone, 2022; Padley, 2022; Russo & Grasso, 2022; Van Dijk, 1996, 2014; Zollo, 2022), register analysis (cf. Hutchinson & Waters, 1987), systemic functional linguistics (cf. Halliday, 1985, 1994; Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014), and contrastive rhetoric (Connor, 1996, 2011)—among others; a discussion of these topics is beyond the scope of this paper, though.

3. Macro/Dialogic pragmatics: Linguistic pragmatics

Aristotle's *Rhetoric* (1984) includes concepts and ideas that are very similar to the concept of 'conversational maxims' covered in Grice's (1975) seminal paper entitled "Logic and conversation" (cf. Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015). This is perhaps a very clear clue that links Greek rhetoric to our understanding of modern (linguistic) pragmatics. Today's pragmatics, however, deviates from ancient Greek rhetoric in two major ways: (a) scope, and (b) audience roles (see section 4 below).

Modern pragmatics—which I would like to call macro pragmatics or dialogic pragmatics (see why in section 4, below)—flourished in the second half of the twentieth century although its forebears can be traced back to ancient times. Allan and Salmani Nodoushan (2015, pp. 149-150) have identified "the Stoics (third century BCE to third century CE), Apollonius (second century CE), Augustine (5th century CE), Abelard (12th century), and Reid (18th century)" as other forebears of pragmatics. They all have presaged "acts of social intercourse between intelligent beings," à la Reid (1785, pp. 72-74), which include (a) assertions, (b) questions, (c) commands, (d) supplications, (e) promises, (f) contracts, (g) prayers, and (h) wishes (Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015). Acts of social intercourse between intelligent beings were later called 'illocutions', and together with the conceptions of 'locutions' and 'perlocutions' comprised the pedestals upon which the modern 'speech act theory' stood (cf. Allan, 2010; Allan & Jaszczolt, 2012; Huang, 2007; Mey, 2001, 2013; Nerlich & Clarke, 1996; Seuren, 1998).

In this connection, Bühler's (1934) 'Organon Model' as well as Jacobson's (1960) model of 'communication functions' can perhaps be called the 'prototypes' of not only the speech act theory—cf. Searle (1969, 1975, 1979, 1981) and Austin (1962, 1963, 1975, 1979)—but also the Hallidayan systemic functional linguistics (Halliday, 1994, 2001, 2003; Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004). Specifically, Jacobson's (1960) model of 'communication functions' was

extremely important in that it stood in sharp contrast to Chomsky's (1968, 1957) 'formal' concept of 'interpretive semantics'. In fact, the seeds of modern pragmatics were first sown when Chomskyan semantics was called into question; Grice's (1975) concepts of (a) 'presuppositions' (or creatures of the dark), (b) 'implicatures', and (c) 'entailments' paved the way for the famous 'cooperative principle' and its maxims of 'relevance/relation', 'manner', 'quantity', and 'quality' to enter the scene. Leech (1983) expatiated upon Grice's (1975) ideas and introduced several other principles of pragmatics. Figure 1 is a schematic representation of Leech's principles.

Figure 1.

Leech's (1983) Conception of the Principles of Pragmatics

The introduction of the cooperative principle marked the beginning of modern pragmatics. Meaning (as Chomsky used to preach) was no longer isolated from context; rather, it was a function of the context of use as well as the common ground shared by the interlocutors in any act of speech (Salmani Nodoushan, 2016b, 2021a). Seen in this light, pragmatics could roughly be defined as the systematic study of the shared knowledge of (a) the 'speakers' and of (b) the 'world'.

Earlier in 1955, Carnap had talked about semiotics and its three branches: (a) semantics, or the study of the relationships that exist between referents and designata—or truth conditions; (b) syntactics, or the study of the relationships among signs; and (c) pragmatics, or the study of the relationships among signs and their functions. Carnap (1955) had argued that pragmatics was the Cinderella of the three, but after Grice (1975) introduced the cooperative principle, this Cinderella finally met her prince on the white horse, and they have lived happily ever after.

Nevertheless, the inception of pragmatics is to a large degree a function of the developments that took place in anthropology and ethnography, both of which

had challenged Chomsky's formalistic conceptions of (a) 'language uniformity', (b) the 'ideal speaker-hearer', and (c) the idealized, context-free treatment of grammar. Anthropology and ethnography argued that, on the one hand, there is no such thing as the 'ideal speaker-hearer', and, on the other hand, this utopian concept is inadequate; for anthropology, there was no language in isolation from social life—a claim that had already been made in Saussure's (1916) 'le langage' (or collective competence) and was later captured in Kristeva's (1989, p. 9) claim that competence "exists only by virtue of a sort of contract signed by the members of a community."

The clear message of this anthropological perspective on language for linguists was that multiple linguistic codes could be used within the same community to satisfy any given function. As such, this anthropological challenge was welcomed by British linguists and the Prague school; they began (a) to free themselves from the shackles of formal grammars, and (b) to recognize the significance of language variation, change, planning, and so forth in connection to social factors. Firth (1957), for instance, introduced the notion of 'contextuality' to discussions of syntax and argued that there is no meaning apart from context. Likewise, Prague school linguists began to consider the social context of linguistic forms in their discussions of linguistics (Dittmar 1976). As such, European structuralism mutated into contextualism, and two new disciplines entered the scene of scientific inquiry: (a) sociolinguistics, and (b) pragmatics.

Both disciplines share one thing: context. They also differ in one thing: context. While both pragmatics and sociolinguistics emphasize the importance of 'context', they differ in how they view it. Pragmatics—at least up to the turn of the century—has endorsed 'interpersonal' context rooted in interlocutors' psychological states and their intentions, beliefs, rationality, etc. Sociolinguistics, on the other hand, has always endorsed a 'social' perspective on context which encompasses (a) the internal organization and infrastructure of a society, (b) its internal differences, (c) its subgroupings, (d) and its intentions—among other things (Levinson, 1983). Note that a discussion of sociolinguistics is beyond the scope of this paper (see Wolfson, 1989).

The consideration of 'interpersonal' context in pragmatics necessitates that speech (acts) should not be analyzed in isolation from interpersonal psychological and social factors such as felicity conditions, power, solidarity, distance, size of imposition, etc. (Salmani Nodoushan, 2016a, 2021b). Searle (1969), for one thing, tied speech acts to speech situations and asserted that the effective performance of each speech act is a function of certain 'felicity' conditions that are read from the context as well as the intricate power and solidarity relations that exist among interlocutors. Searle's (1969) conception of felicity conditions was later captured in Mey's (2001, 2006) theory of 'practs'

and conception of ‘pragmemes’ which assume that “*a fortiori*, there are, strictly speaking, no such ‘things’ as speech acts *per se*, only acts of speech in a situation” (Mey, 2001, p. 24). Capone (2005, 2010, 2012) welcomed Mey’s ideas and expatiated upon them in light of Wittgenstein’s (1953, 1973) ‘language games’ to argue that pragmemes are essentially language games (cf. Capone & Salmani Nodoushan, 2014). A discussion of these topics is beyond the scope of this paper. All in all, modern pragmatics—albeit since the time of Grice (1975; see also Grice, 1989)—has, to date, been firmly founded on at least the following theoretical/philosophical foundations:

- Saussure’s (1916) conceptions of ‘representation’, ‘sign’, ‘reference’, ‘la langue’, ‘la parole’ and ‘le langage’ (see also Kristeva 1989);
- Kantian anti-essentialist philosophy specifically his noumena—roughly defined as brute facts (see Anscombe 1958);
- Wittgenstein’s (1953, 1973) metaphors of the ‘mirror’ and the ‘tool’;
- Jakobson’s Prague school structuralism;
- Philosophical views of Searle, Austin, and Grice; and
- Hallidayan functionalism.

A discussion of these topics is beyond the limits of this paper. The philosophers and linguists listed above as well as the influence of the aforementioned forebears of pragmatics (i.e., the Stoics, Apollonius, Augustine, Abelard, and Reid) can together be assigned to the ‘pre-Gricean’ camp of pragmatics.

Figure 2.

Schematic Representation of the Major Trends in Pragmatics

Aside from this camp, modern pragmatics has ramified into four other major theoretical, and perhaps practical, camps since the time of Grice: (a) the Gricean era, (b) the component era, (c) Mey's era of pragmatic act theory, and (d) Kecskes' era of socio-cognitive pragmatics—in that chronological order. This is, of course, by no means to deny the importance of people like Allan, Bach, Carnap, Horn, Leech, Levinson, Recanati, and Sperber—among others. It should also be emphasized that, within the component era, in turn, four major sub-camps can be identified: (a) speech act theory, (b) neo-Gricean pragmatics including theories of politeness, (c) optimality-theoretic pragmatics, and (d) relevance-theoretic pragmatics. A discussion of these topics is beyond the limits of this paper. Figure 2 (above) is a schematic representation of the major trends in pragmatics.

The movement from structuralism to contextualism did indeed introduce several new concepts to the study of language in context. Chief among them were the concepts of (a) speech situation, (b) speech event, and (c) speech acts (Hymes, 1972). These are, in fact, the very concepts that have informed pragmatics and specifically Mey's (2001) pract theory and Kecskes' (2013) socio-cognitive pragmatics.

In his explanation of the theory of pragmatic acts, Mey (2001) argued that the theory:

[focusses] . . . on the environment in which both speaker and hearer find their affordances, such that the *entire situation* [italics mine] is brought to bear on what can be said in the situation, as well as on what is actually being said. [...T]he emphasis is not on conditions and rules for an individual (or an individual's) speech act, but on characterizing a general situational prototype, capable of being executed in the situation; such a generalized pragmatic act I will call a 'pragmeme'. The instantiated individual pragmatic acts, [...] 'practs', refer to a particular pragmeme in its realizations.

(Mey, 2001, as cited in Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015, p. 150)

It seems as if Mey (2001) has attempted to bring one of the 'affordances', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021c), of sociolinguistics—i.e., its 'social' perspective on context—to bear on his own theory of pragmatics. While (neo-)Gricean pragmatics draws on 'interpersonal' context in its analyses of situated speech, Mey's (2001) pragmemes heavily rely on both 'interpersonal' and 'social' contexts. As such, Mey's theory has adopted a socio-cultural interactional approach to pragmatics (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b). The most important claim made by Mey's theory, however, is that linguistic utterances do not have 'a priori' meanings; meaning is injected into them from outside and when they

are used in a given context or situation. In other words, the direction of interpretation is from without.

Kecskes' (2008, 2010, 2013) 'dialogic' socio-cognitive approach (SCA) to pragmatics, on the other hand, does not completely rule out Mey's claims but defies Occam's razor to argue that the direction of interpretation is from both within and without. According to Kecskes, utterances bring their congenital meanings to bear on communication (Salmani Nodoushan, 2015a); according to Kecskes (2010, p. 2889):

Mey is right emphasizing the importance of situation, environment and extralinguistic factors in meaning construction and comprehension. However, the "wording" of linguistic expressions is as important in shaping meaning as the situation in which they are used and supplemented by extralinguistic factors. Both sides are *equally* [italics mine] important contributors in meaning construction and comprehension.

Although it is not known—to me at least—if both sides might be '*equally*' important, there is some truth in Kecskes' claim; to document his claims, Kecskes (2010) uses situation-bound utterances (SBUs) as counter evidence to challenge Mey's (2001) perspective, arguing that SBUs have 'a priori' meanings that they project from within.

To set the scene for his own 'dialogic' socio-cognitive theory, Kecskes (2013) attacks the traditional bottom-up pragma-semantic perspective (which claims that local pragmatic/semantic phenomena can account for global discursive issues) as well as the more recent top-down 'pragma-dialogue' and 'pragma-discourse' perspectives (which nurture the idea that global social and discursive factors/constraints determine how single utterance are interpreted). As such, he dovetails (a) the 'single utterances' and (b) the 'span of utterances' perspectives to develop his own 'dialogic' and 'socio-cognitive' theory of pragmatics (cf. Kecskes & Zhang, 2009). Building upon Habermas' (1979) conception of human understanding, Kecskes' (2013) Socio-Cognitive Approach (SCA) rules out the 'discourse-as-a-process' perspective to pave the way for his holistic 'dialogic-sequence-and-discourse-segment' perspective on pragmatics (Salmani Nodoushan, 2015a). Discourse is no longer viewed as a 'process' but is seen as a 'structured entity'; SCA presumes a symbiosis between 'emergent' and 'a priori' factors to argue that the direction of meaning is both from within and from without (Kecskes 2013).

Seen from the perspective of SCA, meaning is a function of both an a priori 'individual trait' (i.e., attention, private experience, egocentrism, and salience) and an emergent 'social trait' (i.e., intention, actual situation experience, cooperation, and relevance); the individual and the social traits are mutually

supportive, interactive, and inseparable, and they are incessantly impacted by 'cooperation' (i.e., the intention-directed pragmatic plane measured by relevance) and 'egocentrism' (i.e., the attention-oriented cognitive plane measured by salience). As such, Kecskes' views are informed by Sperber and Wilson's Relevance Theory; nevertheless, SCA is not a facsimile of the Relevance Theory in that SCA measures attention in terms of 'salience' and intention in terms of 'relevance' (cf. Giora, 2003; Sperber & Wilson, 1986; Wilson & Sperber, 2004).

Moreover, Kecskes (2013) argues in favor of two types of context: (a) prior, and (b) emergent. Prior context is already there and is shared by the interlocutors in any act of conversation, but emergent context is the 'actual situational context' that 'emerges' in—and also as a result of—the dynamic flow of real-time conversation. Likewise, common ground is also twofold: (a) core, and (b) emergent. The former is a function of the speakers' earlier interactions and experiences (i.e., his knowledge) within the speech community, but the latter pertains to the relative knowledge that the interlocutors co-construct and/or gain in real-time. Kecskes (2013) argues that 'context', 'common ground', and 'salience' (or the Big Three) have a huge 'washback' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021d) or controlling impact on the dialogic nature of conversation. As such, Kecskes' SCA is, in a way, the 'pragmatic' counterpart of Van Dijk's (2008) views on discourse. Whether this dovetailing of pragmatics and discourse analysis is a (counter-)productive move is the question that calls for a clear answer (see Section 5).

4. Discussion

All in all, modern pragmatics assumes that language is nothing but 'action' (or intention, if you will) and then seeks to show if an action is appropriate in view of certain felicity conditions that have to do with the different elements of the speech situation, the speech event, and the context of use. This is what bridges ancient Greek rhetoric and modern pragmatics. Nevertheless, the former is limited in scope in that it envisages only one type of action: that of 'persuasion'.

As such, ancient Greek rhetoric can perhaps be called micro pragmatics; if pragmatics is defined as the systematic study/analysis of 'intentionality', rhetoric is essentially a microscopic type of pragmatics in that it is concerned with only one kind of intentionality—that of 'persuasion'. Nevertheless, modern pragmatics is concerned with all forms of intentionality—'persuasion' included. As such, modern pragmatics might be called macro pragmatics. This means that ancient Greek rhetoric and modern linguistic pragmatics differ in terms of their 'scopes'. Since the former has a narrow scope while the latter has a much wider scope—that, at the same time, encompasses that of the former—it would not be wrong if we claimed that they stand in inclusional distribution

(i.e., $p \rightarrow q$). This means that rhetoric is part and parcel of linguistic pragmatics, but the reverse is not necessarily true (Figure 3).

The main difference between micro- and macro-pragmatics, however, lies in how they do engage their audience. Unlike Aristotelian rhetoric which brought 'dialectic' to bear on 'persuasion' in a 'unidirectional' form of oration (or discursive action, if you will) which would flow from the rhetor to the audience, modern pragmatics draws on 'dialogic' cooperation, à la Grice (1975) and Leech (1983), among interlocutors in a speech event within a speech situation. Thus, the hearer is no longer an 'adversary' that needs to be persuaded, challenged, or

Figure 3.

The Schematic Representation of the Interface Between Ancient Greek Rhetoric and Modern Linguistic Pragmatics

swayed through eloquent speech; rather, the audience is a cooperative co-creator of the dialogue, working in tandem with the speaker to create the whole speech acts and event. The flow of speech is no longer unidirectional (i.e., from the rhetor to the adversary); it is bidirectional in the sense that both the speaker and the hearer cooperate and provide each other with feedback (cf. Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015). In other words, Grice's (1975) speaker in today's pragmatics is a major player in a cooperative dyad (Allan, 2004) who resorts to cues and clues (cf. Dascal & Weizman, 1987; Weizman & Dascal, 1991)—present in (a) the context and (b) the interlocutor's utterances—to compute intentions and dance to their tune.

By this token, it seems as if speech can be classified into two major classes that I would like to label using the metaphors of 'the television' versus 'the telephone'. Imagine that your television is tuned to a weather forecast channel. You may want to keep asking it "How are you?" The only thing that you get in response, however, is weather forecast. It will always respond with what it wants no matter how many times you turn on your television and ask "How are you?" By way of contrast, when you call someone over the phone, the response to your "How are you?" will, for instance, be "I am well. Thank you. How are you?" While in the metaphor of the television there is no cooperation between you and your television with the aim of co-creating a 'dialogue', in the

metaphor of the telephone, you and your interlocutor cooperate and co-create conversation.

There are, nevertheless, many speech situations (e.g., court rooms, televised debates, etc.) where the nature of speech events (e.g., trials, debates, controversies, etc.) necessitate that the involved parties load their language weapons for the bear—with their magazines filled up with challenge, refutation, persuasion, and so forth. Speech events in such speech situations are not marked by cooperation. Rather, they are marked by adversaryism. Each party creates its own adversarial ‘monologue’ that might be called ‘adversation’, but it definitely cannot be called ‘conversation’. Adversation is always unidirectional, but speech events in speech situations marked by a cooperative dyad turn up into ‘dialogues’ in which both parties work in tandem to co-create the ‘conversation’.

5. Conclusion

All in all, if pragmatics is the systematic study of intentionality, then it can also cover rhetoric since ‘persuasion’ is also a form of intentionality. By the same token, critical discourse analysis is essentially nothing other than pragmatics in action. A similar claim can be made about other disciplines of which the subject matter is text or conversation (e.g., conversation analysis, narrative analysis, etc.). The question that needs a clear, comprehensive and exhaustive answer is: What marks the borders among all of these apparently independent disciplines?

One approach to answering this question might resort to the ideas (e.g., paradigm, crisis, revolution, anomaly, and incommensurability) that Thomas Samuel Kuhn (1962) has presented in his ground-breaking book, *The structure of scientific revolutions*. CDA, for instance, has perhaps come about as a rival to pragmatics since pragmatics did not cover certain topics and issues. Nevertheless, I do not see any methodological, perceptual/observational, or semantic incommensurability in place to necessitate a distinction between CDA and pragmatics, nor between pragmatics and any other linguistic discipline that studies signs, lexemes, adversations, and/or conversations.

Alternatively, I suggest that the term ‘pragmatics’ be reserved for the ‘approach’ side of the coin, and each of the other labels (e.g., conversation analysis, CDA, etc.) be used for the ‘method’ side of the coin. This means that pragmatics is an umbrella term that covers all of the other apparently distinct disciplines that study adversation and dialogue. The implication of this claim is that such disciplines do not differ in theory or subject matter but adopt diverse methods of analysis added that their apparently different methods are intelligible to all pragmaticists; their methods do not show methodological incommensurability to necessitate new borderlines and labels. As such, a

relabeling of CDA and/or rhetoric as 'critical pragmatics' or a relabeling of semantics as 'lexical pragmatics' might not be out of reach. In brief, it is all about 'pragmatics' or even 'sociosemiotics' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b).

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References

- Allan, K. (2004). Aristotle's footprints in the linguist's garden. *Language Sciences*, 26, 317-342.
- Allan, K. (2010). *The western classical tradition in linguistics* (second expanded edition). Equinox.
- Allan, K., & Jaszczolt, K. M. (Eds.). (2012). *The Cambridge handbook of pragmatics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Allan, K., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015). Pragmatics: The state of the art (An online interview with Keith Allan). *International Journal of Language Studies*, 9(3), 147-154.
- Anscombe, G. E. M. (1958). On brute facts. *Analysis*, 18, 69-72.
- Aristotle. (1853). *The organon*. Jazzybee Verlag.
- Austin, J. L. (1962). *How to do things with words*. Clarendon Press.
- Austin, J. L. (1963). *How to do things with words* (2nd ed.). Harvard University Press.
- Austin, J. L. (1975). *How to do things with words* (3rd ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Austin, J. L. (1979). *Philosophical papers* (3rd ed.). Oxford University Press.

- Ayer, A. J. (1936). *Language, truth, and logic*. Victor Gollancz.
- Bacon, F. (1620). *Novum organum*. Bottom of the Hill Publishing.
- Barnes, J. (Ed.). (1984). *The complete works of Aristotle: The revised Oxford translation*. Princeton University Press.
- Battista, A. (2022). Donna Williams' Nobody nowhere and Somebody somewhere: A corpus-based discourse analysis of the author's language as a tool to negotiate one's relationship with the world and the self. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4). 95-116.
- Binkley, R. A. (2004a). Suggestions for teaching ancient Rhetorics: Mesopotamia, problems of origins and reading Enheduanna. In C. S. Lipson & R. A. Binkley (Eds.), *Rhetoric before and beyond the Greeks* (pp. 227-29). SUNY Press.
- Binkley, R. A. (2004b). The rhetoric of origins and the other: Reading the ancient figure of Enheduanna. In C. S. Lipson & R. A. Binkley (Eds.), *Rhetoric before and beyond the Greeks* (pp. 47-64). State University of New York Press.
- Birjandi, P., Alavi, S. M., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2004). *Advanced writing*. Zabankadeh publications.
- Bizzell, P., & Herzberg, B. (Eds.). (1990). *The rhetorical tradition: Readings from classical times to the present*. Bedford Books of St. Martin's Press.
- Borchers, T. A. (2006). *Rhetorical theory: An introduction*. Wadsworth Publishing.
- Bühler, K. (1934). *The theory of language: The representational function of language*. John Benjamin's Publishing Company.
- Capone, A. (2005). Pragmemes (a study with reference to English and Italian). *Journal of Pragmatics*, 37, 1355-1371.
- Capone, A. (2010). On pragmemes again: Dealing with death. *La Linguistique*, 46, 3-21.
- Capone, A. (2012). Indirect reports as language games. *Pragmatics & Cognition*, 20(3), 593-613.

- Capone, A., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2014). On indirect reports and language games: Evidence from Persian. *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia del Linguaggio*, 8(2), 26-42.
- Carnap, R. (1955). Meaning and synonymy in natural languages. *Philosophical Studies*, 6(3), 33-47.
- Chalmers, D. J. (2004). Epistemic two-dimensional semantics. *Philosophical Studies*, 118(1-2), 153-226. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:PHIL.0000019546.17135.e0>
- Chalmers, D. J. (2006). The foundations of two-dimensional semantics. In M. Garcia-Carpintero & J. Macia (Eds.), *Two-dimensional semantics* (pp. 55-140). Clarendon Press.
- Chomsky, N. (1957). *Syntactic structures*. Mouton de Gruyter.
- Chomsky, N. (1968). *Language and mind*. Harcourt, Brace and World.
- Connor, U. (1996). *Contrastive rhetoric*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Connor, U. (2011). *Intercultural rhetoric in the writing classroom*. University of Michigan Press.
- D'Avanzo, S. (2022). Why hire disabled people? Corporate inclusive policies by three tech giants. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4), 137-156.
- Dascal, M., & Weizman, E. (1987). Contextual exploitation of interpretation clues in text understanding: An integrated model. In J. Verschueren & M. Bertuccelli-Papi (Eds.), *The pragmatic perspective* (pp. 31-46). John Benjamins.
- Davidson, D. (1967). Truth and meaning. *Synthese*, 17(1), 304-323.
- De Saussure, F. (1916). *Course in general linguistics*. McGraw Hill.
- Dittmar, N. (1976). *Sociolinguistics. A critical survey of theory and application*. Edward Arnold.
- Fairclough, N. (1989). *Language and power*. Taylor & Francis.

- Firth, J. R. (1957). *A synopsis of linguistic theory: Studies in linguistic analysis*. Blackwell.
- Foster, J. A. (1976). Meaning and truth theory. In G. Evans & J. McDowell (Eds.), *Truth and meaning: Essays in semantics* (pp. 1-32). Clarendon Press.
- Frege, F. L. G. (1879). *Begriffsschrift*. Louis Nebert.
- Frege, F. L. G. (1892[1960]). Über sinn und bedeutung (On sense and reference). *Zeitschrift für Philosophie und philosophische Kritik*, 100, 25-50.
- Frege, F. L. G. (1906). Kurze Übersicht meiner logischen Lehren? In M. Beaney (Ed.), *The Frege reader* (pp. 299-300). Basil Blackwell.
- Giora, R. (2003). *On our mind: Salience, context and figurative language*. Oxford university Press.
- Grice, H. P. (1957). Meaning. *Philosophical Review*, 66, 377-388.
- Grice, H. P. (1975). Logic and conversation. In P. Cole & J. L. Morgan (Eds.), *Syntax and semantics 3: Speech acts* (pp. 22-40). Academic Press.
- Grice, H. P. (1989). Logic and conversation. In H. P. Grice (Ed.), *Studies in the way of words* (pp. 22-40). Harvard University Press.
- Grice, H. P. (1989). *Studies in the way of words*. Harvard University press.
- Habermas, J. (1979). *Communication and the evolution of society*. Beacon Press.
- Haiman, J. (1983). Iconic and economic motivation. *Language*, 59, 781-819.
- Haiman, J. (1992). Iconicity. In R. E. Asher (Ed.), *International encyclopedia of linguistics* (pp. 191-195). Oxford University Press.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1985). *An introduction to functional grammar*. Edward Arnold.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1994). *An Introduction to functional grammar* (2nd ed.). Edward Arnold.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (2001). Is the grammar neutral? Is the grammarian neutral? In J. de Villiers & R. J. Stainton (Eds.), *Communication in linguistics* (pp. 179-204). Editions du GREF.

- Halliday, M. A. K. (2003). Introduction: On the 'architecture' of human language. In M. A. K. Halliday & J. J. Webster (Eds.), *On language and linguistics* (pp. 1-29). Continuum.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Matthiessen, C. M. I. M. (2004). *An introduction to functional grammar* (3rd ed.). Arnold.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Matthiessen, C. M. I. M. (2014). *Halliday's introduction to functional grammar* (4th ed.). Routledge.
- Hallo, W. W. (2004). The birth of rhetoric. In C. S. Lipson & R. A. Binkley (Eds.), *Rhetoric before and beyond the Greeks* (pp. 25-46). State University of New York Press.
- Hoskisson, P. Y., & Boswell, G. M. (2004). Neo-Assyrian rhetoric: The example of the third campaign of Sennacherib (704-681 BC). In C. S. Lipson & R. A. Binkley (Eds.), *Rhetoric before and beyond the Greeks* (pp. 65-78). State University of New York Press.
- Huang, Y. (2007). *Pragmatics*. Oxford University Press.
- Hutchinson, T., & Waters, A. (1987). *English for specific purposes: A learning centered approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hymes, D. (1967). Models of the interaction of language and social setting. *Journal of Social Issues*, 23(2), 8-28.
- Jakobson, R. (1960). Closing statement: Linguistics and poetics. In T. A. Sebeok (Ed.), *Style in language* (pp. 350-377). MIT Press.
- Kecskes, I. (2008). Dueling contexts: A dynamic model of meaning. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 40(3), 385-406.
- Kecskes, I. (2010). Situation-bound utterances as pragmatic acts. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 42(11), 2889-2897.
- Kecskes, I. (2013). *Intercultural pragmatics*. Oxford University Press.
- Kecskes, I., & Zhang, F. (2009). Activating, seeking and creating common ground: A socio-cognitive approach. *Pragmatics & Cognition*, 17(2), 331-355.
- Kristeva, J. (1989). *Language: The unknown*. Columbia University Press.

- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The structure of scientific revolutions*. University of Chicago Press.
- Leech, G. N. (1983). *Principles of pragmatics*. Longman.
- Levinson, S. C. (1983). *Pragmatics*. Cambridge University Press.
- MacDonald, M. (Ed.). (2017). *The Oxford handbook of rhetorical studies*. Oxford University Press.
- Mey, J. L. (2001). *Pragmatics: An introduction* (2nd ed.). Blackwell.
- Mey, J. L. (2006). Pragmatic acts. In K. Brown (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of language and linguistics* (pp. 5-11). Elsevier.
- Mey, J. L. (2013). Across the abyss: The pragmatics-semantics interface revisited. *Intercultural Pragmatics*, 10(3), 487-494.
- Nerlich, B., & Clarke, D. D. (1996). *Language, action, and context: The early history of pragmatics in Europe and America, 1780-1930*. John Benjamins.
- Padley, R. H. (2022). Shame, discrimination and disability: Unveiling narratives of obesity. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4), 43-64.
- Raffone, A. (2022). "Her leg didn't fully load in": A digitally-mediated social-semiotic critical discourse analysis of disability hate speech on TikTok. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4), 17-42.
- Reid, T. (1785). *Essays on the intellectual powers of man*. John Bell.
- Russo, K. E., & Grasso, A. (2022). Coping with dis/ableism in Twitter discourse: A corpus-based critical appraisal analysis of the Hidden Disabilities Sunflower Lanyard case. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4), 65-94.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015a). Book review [Review of the book *Intercultural Pragmatics* by Istvan Kecskes]. *Pragmatics and Society*, 6(1), 152-156. <https://doi.org/10.1075/ps.6.1.08nod>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2015b). The secret life of slurs from the perspective of reported speech. *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia del Linguaggio*, 9(2), 92-112.

- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016a). On the functions of swearing in Persian. *Journal of Language Aggression and Conflict*, 4(2), 234-254.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016b). Rituals of death as staged communicative acts and pragmemes. In A. Capone & J. L. Mey (Eds.), *Interdisciplinary studies in pragmatics, culture and society* (pp. 925-959). Springer.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2018). Which view of indirect reports do Persian data corroborate? *International Review of Pragmatics*, 10(1), 76-100. <https://doi.org/10.1163/18773109-00901008>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021a). Demanding versus asking in Persian: Requestives as acts of verbal harassment. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 15(1), 27-46.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021b). Language and socialization? It is all about sociosemiotics. *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia del Linguaggio*, 15(2), 209-225. <https://doi.org/10.4396/2021207>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021c). Test affordances or test function? Did we get Messick's message right? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 15(3), 127-140.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021d). Washback or backwash? Revisiting the status quo of washback and test impact in EFL contexts. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 8(3), 869-884.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2022). Breaking out of the Gricean vicious cycle: Let's divorce semantics and just agree that there is no meaning in language. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(3), 33-60.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2023). Native experts and reputable journals as points of reference: A study on research-article discussions. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 10(2), 562-574.
- Searle, J. R. (1969). *Speech acts: An essay in the philosophy of language*. Cambridge University Press.
- Searle, J. R. (1975). A taxonomy of illocutionary acts. In K. Gunderson (Ed.), *Language, mind and knowledge* (pp. 344-369). University of Minnesota Press.

- Searle, J. R. (1979). A taxonomy of illocutionary acts. In J. R. Searle (Ed.), *Expression and meaning* (pp. 1-29). Cambridge University Press.
- Searle, J. R. (1981). Analytic philosophy and mental phenomena. *Midwest Studies in Philosophy*, 6, 405-424.
- Seuren, P. A. M. (1998). *Western linguistics: An historical introduction*. Blackwell.
- Sperber, D., & Deirdre W. (1986). *Relevance: Communication and cognition*. Blackwell.
- Stark, R. J. (2008). Some aspects of Christian mystical rhetoric, philosophy, and poetry. *Philosophy and Rhetoric*, 41(3), 260-77.
- Van Dijk, T. A. (1996). Discourse and cognition in society. In D. C. Mitchell (Ed.), *Communication theory today* (pp. 107-126). Pergamon Press.
- Van Dijk, T. A. (2008). *Discourse and context: A sociocognitive approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- Van Dijk, T. A. (2014). *Discourse and knowledge: A sociocognitive approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- Walker, J. (2000). *Rhetoric and poetics in antiquity*. Oxford University Press.
- Weizman, E., & Dascal, M. (1991). On clues and cues: Strategies of text-understanding. *Journal of Literary Semantics*, 20(1), 18-30.
- Wilson, D., & Sperber, D. (2004). Relevance theory. In L. Horn & G. Ward (Eds.), *The handbook of pragmatics* (pp. 607-632). Wiley-Blackwell.
- Wittgenstein, L. (1953). *Philosophical investigations*. Blackwell.
- Wittgenstein, L. (1973). *Philosophical investigations* (3rd ed.). Pearson.
- Wolfson, N. (1989). *Perspectives: Sociolinguistics and TESOL*. Newbury House Publishers.
- Zollo, S. A. (2022). Mental disabilities: Fighting stigma and discrimination in public service announcements. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4), 117-136.